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Child-Free by Choice: Why are some Filipino Millennials Reluctant to have Children?

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Abstract

The study intended to provide additional information in order to widen the perspective and knowledge as a child-free. This study will help society gain insight into why Filipino millennials choose to not have children, as well as their social advantages and disadvantages. Child-free is a social issue that is not often discussed and has not received much attention in society. There are negative and positive reactions whenever other people know someone who's voluntarily not wanting to have a child in the future. In order to know the factors that are causing Filipino millennials to be child-free, the researchers used descriptive research design and made an open-ended questionnaire, which involved 10 Filipino child-free millennials in Metro Manila. After gathering the data, the researchers utilized thematic analysis to thematize themes and codes needed for the study. The results indicate the reasons why Filipino millennials are reluctant to have children, with the most common answers being their childhood upbringing, experiences, financial ability to have children, and their desired life satisfaction. Along with the results, it also revealed the concerns of the participants and the stereotyping they experienced, they received criticisms from their family, workplace, and their surroundings wherein they opened up their decision and was not accepted by the society.

Keywords: *child-free, millennials, social norms*

Introduction

The researchers conducted a study to explore the causes of why some Filipino millennials are deciding not to have children. They looked at the current societal trends and issues concerning the state of being child-free and sought to understand why some Filipino millennials are deciding not to have children.

Tudy and Gauran-Tudy (2020) suggest that society has a significant impact on people's lives and has the power to shape their attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions of society. Filipino millennials are breaking this tradition, as being child-free has become one of the important social issues that needs further discussion. There are reasons why Filipino millennials are reluctant to have children, and these reasons are examined and discussed in the later part of the study. Being child-free is either a voluntary or involuntary choice for anyone. It is identified as a voluntary choice if couples or women decide not to have a child at all, and an involuntary child-free state occurs when couples or women are not able to bear children due to health concerns.

The pattern of society in terms of childbearing has changed over the years, and there is a great difference between generational views about the state of being child-free. This has been explored through studies such as Fry et al. (2020) which compared millennials to other women of a similar age in 1965. In western countries, the usual age of first-time mothers is now 21 to 26, while for first-time fathers it has risen from 27 to 31. Additionally, millennials are still hesitant to change their marital status due to financial security and may not have found their ideal spouse yet. Barroso et al. (2020) indicated that many millennials are still not married in today's generation, which is unlike the previous generation, in which when they turn 18 years old and above, it is most likely that they will start to have their own families and bear children. Millennials now prefer to live with their family rather than consider having a family of their own, as they want to support their family financially.

Millennials' reasons for not wanting to have kids include not being financially prepared, overpopulation, pandemic, and focusing on their own relationships, careers, and selves. There is a stigma attached to women who decide not to have kids, and some delay having a child or choose to be child-free due to cost. Hence, additional studies are needed to explore more causes.

Research studies have found that millennial women have been delaying parenthood for a long time, with the number of these women having doubled since 1970. Pew Research Center also revealed that 37% of child-free millennials prefer not to have kids and do not intend to have any in the future. In 2018, the number of newborns hit its lowest level in 32 years, and the rate has been slowly dropping in the U.S. since then. A women's report revealed that they want 2.6 children yet end up having only 1.73, on average. These factors need to be explored thoroughly to understand how millennials come up with the decision of not wanting to have a child.

The decision-making process of couples regarding childbearing includes socioeconomic factors, such as the amount of salary they have. A study conducted by Maghinang (2019) found that having children is not fundamentally wrong, but it can be time- and money-consuming. Additionally, financial issues such as the recession have caused millennials to suffer from financial difficulties. Millennials also consider their ability to become a good provider for their future kids, and it is better to not have kids if they cannot afford to fulfill their parental responsibilities.

A study by Carmichael and Whittaker, 2007, suggested that some women decided not to bear children simply because they did not consider themselves fit to become mothers. Cain (2013) referred to the population that views motherhood as not one of the mandatory

stages of life. There are some millennial couples who are still not fully decided whether to have a child or not, a decision-making process that involves their different opinions and perceptions about the status of their relationship and the possible effects it may impose. Little research has been done on millennial couples where their partners prefer not to have children.

The most important details are that some people with mental health issues are hesitant to bear a child due to the potential health risks and physiologic effects of the pregnancy. Additionally, millennials are more reluctant to get exposed to prenatal care due to their fear of having a child (Stahl, 2020).

Cabonce et al. (2019) and Shpancer (2019) found that couples who choose to be child-free still get a lot of judgment from individuals. However, child-free individuals show no regret in choosing this path, despite being pressured by society, religion, relatives, friends, and family members. They should live the life they have always dreamed of for themselves, and should not be ashamed of their decision as long as they are not hurting anyone.

This research study sought to understand why Filipino millennials prefer to become child-free, making it more accessible to the public. The results of the research paper should break the norms set by the old generation that result in stigmatization and enhance acceptance of the concept of becoming child-free in Philippine society.

Research Questions

This study determined the reasons why Filipino millennials preferred to be child-free. Specifically, it answered the question:

1. Why are some Filipino millennials reluctant to have children?

Literature Review

Child-free

Gouni et al. (2022) defined child-free as not having children in your life. If a person is unable to conceive for unknown medical reasons, it is considered involuntary, while having no children on purpose is known as voluntary. Being child-free may be a source of embarrassment, generating issues not just for the couples and their marriage, but also for their social image. People have sought to discover other ways to avoid the negative repercussions of not having children at an early age.

According to Siegel, H. (2017), being child-free is egocentric based on their reasons, their reasons were said that they had known from the start that they did not want children, and many said they became clear about this when they were playing with their toys, and they made no changes to their decision. From adolescence to menopause, they said that they realize that having children is not their path. Others included the environment the children will grow up because of overpopulation, traumatic childhoods, mental and physical disorders that they experienced in their life that made them decide to avert carrying and delivery, and of course, the economic state of the country.

Child-free individuals firmly value their whole body, as well as their health because they are scared of being exposed to any disease that they could get during and after pregnancy. The decision to be child-free is not only applied to women, but also to men who opt to have a child. Studies have shown that many people have little experience with taking care of children, and they do not feel like they are suitable as parents (Höglund & Hildingsson, 2022). From the perspective of voluntarily childfree women, motherhood is a continuance commitment and it is a burden for many women, and having a child is an inconvenience for them in reaching their goals (Parlak, & Tekin, 2020). Choosing to have a child is a decision of both men and women, but childcare is a duty of most women as a result of social construct or cultural norms.

In a Filipino study by Cabonce et al., (2019), it is rare for couples to settle not to have kids, especially in a country that is known for being family-centered such as the Philippines. In this present time, the tradition of older generations is still followed by some people in the provinces. The Filipino child-free couples choose to break the stigma of all people who bravely choose not to have a child in their lives.

Societal Views Regarding Child-free

Many boomers are still in the "young elderly" category, where their health is strong, their energy and income appear limitless, and their main focus is finding enjoyable ways to spend their retirement. However, over time, health can deteriorate and complete independence may become impossible. Moreover, a third of Americans were unmarried over a decade ago, according to research. Nearly one-third of the Baby Boom generation was divorced and a third had never been married. Only 10% of unmarried baby boomers were widowed, though this percentage has probably increased in the decade since (Phillips, 2019).

While Australian women in their middle age were discriminated against because they were not referred to as "mothers". Individuals believed that motherhood is strongly intertwined with being a woman in the experiences and perceptions of women, and women who do not have children were less likely to be seen as women since they do not have a child with them. Women who choose not to have children are reportedly stereotyped, humiliated, and socially marginalized in the community. Because most social groups are mother's groups or child-focused groups, middle-aged women who had planned not to have a child or do not have a child are completely

hampered by not having anyone in the community. They feel excluded, which causes them to refrain from participating and forming social connections with people in the community (Graham et al., 2019).

Rate of Child-free

Not just in the modern generation, but primates also have female competition and selective pressure may also be considered during human evolution. This can be a result of social stress that can affect full-term pregnancy and child survival. Thus, fertility behavior in patrilocal monogamous society was also affected by this competition. Also, at an early age, western women who have reproductive problems that are associated with infertility and ovulatory delay are the ones who have lower self-esteem and lack of support from family and friends. It shows that the presence of other women can affect the birth rates and their reproductivity with their rivals since they see it as a competition (Lahdenperä et al., 2017). In the study of Neal and Neal (2021), in 1970, it was already recognized as the child-free concept for individuals and defined as people who decided not to have kids. With an estimated 7.8 million adults in Michigan, over 2 million of them are not willing to have children and identified themselves as child-free adults. Not just individuals, but 35% of them are couples and also do not want to have kids. The rates of married women who were child-free ranged from a low of 2.2% to a high of 9% in 1995, and recently childfree women rates between 2006 and 2010 ranged at 6%. However, recently, women who are not planning to have children have a higher rate of 23%. During the 20th century, the fertility rate in Sweden dropped from 4 to 1.5 and similar disapproval was also noted in Europe. Nevertheless, there was a comparison between Nordic countries with other countries where the rates stabilized around 1.7 to 2.0. The stabilization resulted in an adaptation to a more gender-equal country or society, where men and women have equality in opportunities and support in combining work and family life based on dominant theory. All of these began in the 1960s when equality, sexuality, contraceptives, and abortion are more concerns of men and women. While in 1970, there were a lot of benefits that the state offered like well-paid and extensive parental leave, giving child benefits, and childcare or daycare centers changed (Bodin et al., 2021).

Factors that influence Filipino millennials to be child-free

Financial State

Considering the financial status of every couple who wants to start a family and have a child is an important part of planning. Numerous couples ended up leaving each other because they did not plan their future with their children. Not being able to plan their future and being financially unstable are the reasons why some Filipino millennial prefers not to have kids. People who have their children because they got separated from their partners are struggling not only with their mental health but also with their financial responsibility. Usually, solo parents do not receive support from their partners for their children. Having financial problems in supporting their children alone was determined to be difficult and stressful (Stack & Meredith, 2017).

Physical Health and Mental Health

There are several factors to take into account when deciding whether or not to have a child, especially one that will impact your future together. It is not a simple procedure, being able to communicate with each other during difficult times requires time and patience. Decisions like these are not always easy to make. The couple must carefully consider several factors, as difficult situations may arise when one person wants children and the other does not. On this matter, the couple must be mentally ready to decide. The process of contemplating this decision may also raise concerns about the couples' mental health, especially if your partner wants to bear a child and the other is not. Being child-free is a long-term plan because the results will be permanent and will last a lifetime, therefore the couple must be ready in all aspects (Lorenzo-Echeverri, 2020).

Personal Experience

The study of Saraela, (2020) stated how individual histories of partnerships are related to child-free situations. Marriage after delivery, separation from marriages, and cohabitation without marriage are all common denominators, as they are secularized in societies. Thus, child-free assessments must include information on partnership histories. However, this possibility is uncommon since not having a spouse is a major factor in being child-free, has been conducted on how people become single, and how their marital histories influenced the likelihood of not having children in the future. The expense of living and having a kid is a challenging issue for millennials who want to explore their life by traveling and being independent. Being childfree is not a selfish choice because if it is, then people need to question those parents who bear a child but do not give them their rights to education. As an alternative, we may disregard the "selfish" label and allow individuals to make the decisions that are best for themselves, including motherhood. Some individuals think that people without children do not give back, do not contribute to their communities, or do not make a difference in the world. Studies show that those without children volunteer just as much as parents in their communities (Pawloski, 2019).

The researchers gathered and reviewed a variety of related literature. It provided the researchers with a wealth of information that was extremely useful in providing an in-depth understanding of the overall reasons and viewpoints of people who chose not to have children. Various studies focus on the impact of not having a child, as well as stereotypes and judgment associated with individuals endure when they chose to be child-free. This research study conducts a further investigation regarding this topic to provide additional knowledge based on opinions, information, and rational argument about the study, in order to fill in the identified gaps.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative approach was used to collect the data for this study and thematic analysis was used to analyze the data gathered from the participants.

Participants

The participants in this research were carefully chosen to meet the requirements of the study. They are all-gender Filipino millennial citizens who chose not to have children and were born between 1981 to 1996. Additionally, the study did not restrict the data collection to sexuality or civil status in order to acquire participants' viewpoints. There were ten millennials in this study, gathered from Metro Manila using a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique that involves selecting sample units based on considerations relevant to the study. The participants were chosen using a purposive sampling method in order to focus on the responses of millennials who voluntarily chose not to have children. To gather information that is appropriate and relevant to the research study and to produce a precise conclusion.

The participants in this study consist of ten (10) single Filipino millennials who chose to be child-free. Eight (8) of the interviewees for this study were female, and two (2) were male. In terms of the age bracket of participants, they range from 26 to 37 years old. Three (3) of the respondents were 27 years old, while two (2) participants for ages 26, 28, and 35, and only one (1) was 37 years old. All respondents resided in Metro Manila, with three (3) participants hailing from Quezon City and the other seven (7) participants are from various cities in and around Metro Manila, including San Juan City, Manila City, Pasay City, Valenzuela City, Las Pinas City, and Makati City.

Instrument

The researchers created an open-ended questionnaire that was validated and examined by professionals in the field of Psychology, the instrument was good enough to elicit responses. Using an open-ended questionnaire, researchers allowed the respondents to give answers in a free form. In the interview, respondents were asked about their perceptions and experiences of being child-free by choice. The researchers created questions based on the three components that were sought in this study, and let the participants respond freely, allowing for more detailed answers and opinions. There were three components of the study; first, the emerging reason that motivates Filipino millennials to become child-free. Second, the emerging concerns that arise in the state of being a child-free Filipino millennial. Lastly, the common stereotype inclined toward child-free Filipino millennials.

Procedure

Purposive sampling method was used to find participants suited for the study. Filipino child-free millennials residing in Metro Manila, Philippines were chosen as participants. When the researchers accumulated ten (10) participants, an informed consent form consisting of principles, confidentiality, and ethical considerations were sent to their Gmail accounts. The researchers conducted an online or virtual interview through Zoom. Additionally, before the researchers started the interview, an introductory statement was discussed with the participants to understand the purpose of the interview. The data gathering was conducted over a two-week time period, while the online interview lasted for thirty (30) to sixty (60) minutes depending on how the participant answered.

Ethical Considerations

The study aimed to offer additional information to broaden people's perspectives and knowledge about child-free and will aid society in understanding why Filipino millennials chose not to have children. The researchers gathered information from the participants through a virtual interview, wherein informed consent was given on their respective emails before participating in the study. This includes information about what is expected from them and what to expect during the interview, as well as the fact that the virtual interview will be recorded. Participants were also not forced to participate in this study since they have the right to withdraw and not continue the interview if the study harms them. Additionally, participants were cited by an assigned number as a substitute for their names, while data or recordings were discarded properly and securely for confidentiality and privacy.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the answers to the questionnaires distributed to the field. The said data were presented in tabular form per the specific questions posited in the problem statement.

Table 1. *Emerging Themes*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Reasons of Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsibilities • Personal Choices • Life Challenges • Factors and Reasons

Common Concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural Views, Beliefs and Perspectives • Benefits • Child-Free Returns • Socio-economic Settings and Circumstances • Stagnant Choice • Societal Prospects and Expectations
Common Stereotypes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beliefs, Views and Perspectives • Downsides and Shortcomings • Adverse Sight

Reasons of Motivation

The present study found that Filipino millennials are motivated on being child-free based on positive and negative factors from their early adulthood up to recently. It was revealed that not having children is their personal choice. The majority of them represented responsibilities as motivation since having a child means having substantial accountabilities. Meanwhile, life challenges, cultural views, beliefs, perspectives, and benefits added factors as their motivation for their decision. This revealed that Filipino millennials experienced financial, environmental, social, and mental issues including traumas that became additional factors for these motivations to be child-free individuals. Moreover, having adequate benefits which include more time with themselves, traveling, saving up money, and career opportunities strengthened the foundation to just invest in themselves for their personal goals and simply adore what they have without introducing another human being.

Common Concerns

The study revealed that the emerging concerns of being child-free Filipino millennials have an effect on society's future. They presumed there would be a positive change in socioeconomic circumstances when people tried not to procreate because it would lessen the population. Other than that, some point out that their child-free decision did not change their perspectives and choices because they believed their choice would not be temporary, even if they received challenges in their life as they chose this lifestyle.

Common Stereotypes

The study identified the common stereotypes towards child-free Filipino millennials and found that society does not fully perceive and support child-free living among millennials. Since child reluctance is still taboo in the Philippines, many child-free Filipino millennials struggle to fit in with societal norms. Some also see the shortcomings of being child-free individuals, which somehow affect their physical and mental health because of the traditional beliefs that society is throwing at them. However, even though many people partially support being child-free, people who choose to be child-free are still subjected to adverse sight and rationalizations from the people of the society. Since being a childfree individual is not yet entirely accepted by society, many people are still not yet found to the new beliefs that generations are opening up to and, therefore, often criticize those choosing to live a child-free lifestyle.

Conclusions

This research supports destigmatizing the concept of individuals choosing not to bear a child in society and educating the community regarding the concept of child-free. Furthermore, to introduce and fill their knowledge regarding this topic since there are few research studies conducted, especially in Asian countries that are known for being family-oriented. This study revealed that there are positive and negative factors that impact Filipino millennials' decisions such as life challenges, cultural views, beliefs, perspectives, and benefits. Aside from that, it also revealed the emerging concerns of being child-free in the future generation, including its impact on the socioeconomic circumstances when the population lessens. Lastly, the stereotypes associated with Filipino individuals based on the beliefs and perspective of society gain an adverse view to the decision of individuals in being child-free. It revealed the downsides and shortcomings to life of individuals who opt to have kids.

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